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Solventless synthesis of 1-(α -aminoalkyl) naphthols, betti bases, catalyzed by nanoparticle Fe₃O₄ at room temperature

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Abstract

A series of 1-(α -aminoalkyl) naphthols were synthesized expeditiously in good yields and selectivity from 2-naphthol, alkylamines and aldehydes in the presence of nanoparticle Fe₃O₄ at room temperature in solvent-free conditions.

Keyword

Betti base, Heterogeneous catalysis, Solvent-free conditions, Multicomponent synthesis,